

Data for Policy CIC

Sub-Saharan Africa Engagement Programme

November 2024

Shaping the Future of Governance with Data & AI...

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Fast-growing global expert community of interest –
but proactive effort and investment needed to ensure proportional involvement from Global South

Data for Policy CIC Sub-Saharan Africa Programme

Stakeholder Consultations

28-31 March 2023 Nairobi, Kenya –
Maximizing SSA's Impact in the
Global Data for Policy Dialogue

23-27 October 2023 Accra, Ghana –
Advancing Data & AI Competency for
Effective and Trustworthy Decision-
Making in SSA

8 July 2024 London, UK –
Understanding, Facilitating, and
Connecting AI and Data Science
Futures in SSA's Public Sector

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Partners & Collaborators

- African Institute for Development Policy (AFIDEP)
 - Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis (KIPPRA)
 - Institute of Statistical, Social and Economic Research (ISSER, University of Ghana)
 - Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa (CSEA, Nigeria)

 - AfriLabs
 - Alliance for a Green Revolution in Africa (AGRA)
 - Council of Governors (COG, Kenya)
 - Africa Evidence Network (AEN)
 - African Development Bank (AfDB)
 - AI4A (Artificial Intelligence for Africa)
 - Kenyatta University's Women Empowerment Hub (Wee HUB)

 - African Centre of Meteorological Applications for Development (ACMAD)
 - Afrobarometer
 - Regional Network of Agricultural Policy Research Institutes (ReNapri) - Ghana Branch
 - RAIN (Research and Innovation Network)
 - g7+ Group of Fragile and Conflict-Affected States

 - African Union (AU)
 - Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS)
 - Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA)
 - Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS)
 - Southern African Development Community (SADC)
 - Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD)
- Cambridge University Press
 - Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF)
 - Evans School Policy Analysis and Research Group (EPAR), University of Washington
 - Centre for Science & Policy (CSaP), University of Cambridge
 - UCL Computer Science (GovTech)
 - Imperial Data Science Institute & Imperial Policy Forum
 - The GovLab & NYU

 - The World Bank (WB)
 - Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD)
 - Industry Data for Society Partnership
 - Development Data Partnership
 - Partnership on AI
 - Global Partnership for Sustainable Development
 - Data Collaboratives

 - Migration Data Portal (part of the IOM's Global Migration Data Analysis Centre)
 - International Organisation for Migration (IOM)

 - AgriTech and ClimateTech companies
 - African Technology Start-ups ecosystem
 - ITC Companies (MTN, Airtel, Orange, etc.)
 - DevAfrique (Policy Portal)

Impact from Data for Policy CIC's SSA Engagement Programme

Phase 1 (May 2022 – May 2024)
funded by

BILL & MELINDA
GATES *foundation*

SSA Engagement
Programme was
announced at
Data for Policy 2022 –
Seattle Conference

Opportunities and Threats Shaping the Data for Policy Ecosystem: SSA Focus

Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growing Global Interest: Strong international and regional focus on data-driven policy formulation and responsible innovation. • Mission-Driven Innovation: Rising demand to address grand challenges like climate change adaptation, equity, and gender balance. • Priority on Africa: Emphasis on African agriculture, the digital economy, inclusion of women and girls, and climate change. • Skills Gap: High demand for data science and policy expertise due to global talent shortages. • Collaboration Spaces: Growing need for platforms fostering knowledge exchange and innovative partnerships. • Catalytic Funding Opportunities: Major interest from funders (e.g., BMGF) and strong engagement from SSA stakeholders. • Regional Leadership: Established collaborations to lead and support strategic SSA programmes. • Open-Access Incentives: Significant interest in publishing in the Data for Policy space, driving innovation and accessibility. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Limitations: Poor availability, quality, and accessibility of data; weak digital infrastructure and capacity. • Instability Risks: Political and economic instability, including limited leadership or political will. • Mismatch of Timelines: Disconnect between policy implementation cycles and research timelines. • Economic Trends: Market downturns may reduce investments in data-driven policy solutions. • Donor Shifts: Changing priorities among donors, posing funding challenges. • Competitive Pressure: Emerging competition from African and international institutions. • Rapid Ecosystem Changes: Need for agility in adapting to evolving data and policy landscapes. • Stakeholder Fragmentation: Lack of coordination, exacerbating inequalities and marginalising underdeveloped systems.

What Sets Us Apart: Core Strengths

- **Strategic Independence:** Operates under a unique CIC structure, enabling flexibility and autonomy.
- **World-Class Networks:** Extensive collaborations with global experts and institutions.
- **Proven Programme Efficacy:** Conference series, journal, and community-building initiatives drive measurable impact.
- **Innovative Knowledge Exchange:** Pioneering multi-disciplinary, multi-channel global practices for transformative knowledge sharing.
- **Leadership Across the Value Chain:** Strong focus on integrating data, policy, and investment for long-term solutions.
- **Established Brand and Credibility:** Recognised and respected across fields, with a skilled staff and an influential advisory group.
- **Resource Efficiency with Global Impact:** Maximising impact through agile, cost-effective resource management.
- **Forward-Looking Strategy:** Focus on expanding and diversifying funding sources to sustain growth and innovation.

Our approach revolves around three main axes

Global (disciplines, sectors, geographies)

- Scale of challenges & rewards
- Interconnectedness
- Synergies

Open/collaborative innovation

- Transparency, accessibility & equity
- Additivity, reusability (to do more with less)
- Dynamic knowledge exchange

Advanced computation & (data-driven) knowledge generation

- Focus on analysis, methodology & techniques (often under unrealistic assumptions)
- Foundational sciences - computer science, statistics, mathematics
- Relatively long-term incentives, potential applications & impact
- Low-risk problem contexts

Policy & practice

- Focus on complex socio-economic-political problems & policy (often without in depth understanding of available tools & methodologies)
- Social sciences & humanities – political science, economics, laws, ethics, philosophy
- Immediate demand-driven or bound by political timeframes & investment decisions
- High-stakes problem contexts

Traditional/proprietary innovation

- IP protection & direct rewards
- Control over innovation & impact
- Established markets & financial models
- Safety & security concerns / prioritisation
- Clarity in ownership & responsibility

Local

- Tailored solutions & direct impact
- Focus & resource efficiency
- Local knowledge & context
- Sovereignty

Realising Data for Policy Community Vision and Values

- Global partnership, collaboration & knowledge exchange spaces
- Monitoring and reporting the field development
- Holistic R&D capacity innovating for the ecosystem

- Tools and practices
- Incentives for participation
- Models for financial sustainability
- Leadership for culture change

- Mission-driven exploration outside of academic cycles that is responsive to policy needs
- Research translation skills to implement data-driven solutions in specific policy contexts
- Monitoring, evaluation & risk assessment of data-driven knowledge generation for potential use in policy contexts

- Mission-driven exploration outside of policy cycles to build actionable insights from data-driven research & innovation
- Data & technology literacy and skills development to confidently work with researchers and innovators
- Monitoring, evaluation & risk assessment of socio-economic contexts for data-driven innovation

- Proprietary**
- Business in the public interest & social entrepreneurship models
 - Innovation sandboxes & pipeline to policy
 - Responsible innovation & regulation (transparency, explainability, accountability, fairness, safety & security, legitimacy etc.)

- Local/National**
- Promoting local leadership & expertise for local solutions
 - Supporting local knowledge base with global experience
 - Identifying local strengths & priorities
 - Scaling up the visibility & impact of successful local projects

Our Theory of Change: SSA Focus

Inputs	Processes	Outputs	Outcomes	Impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic talent (executive, program leadership, administration) • Dedicated funds to incentivise & support SSA stakeholders for participation • Dedicated funds for strategic academic partnerships to support R&D and training programs • Hybrid operational infrastructure, support staff and logistics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal regional consortium with transparent governance model • Holistic DfP regional inclusion program • Strategic leadership development program • Systematic R&D capacity supporting community development <p>* All our processes are scalable to maximize impact at varying revenue and investment levels</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportional representation of SSA stakeholders in all DfP committee structures, authorship base, and the reviewer pool • Strategic collaborations with SSA regional stakeholders, supporting them for regionally focused projects over multiple years through an open call - addressing climate change adaptation, digital economy, agricultural development, and women's empowerment • Individuals directly supported to participate in the DfP regional consortium, conferences, and journal publishing • Regional policy-makers and practitioners supported through the fellowship program to develop leadership skills and capacity • Research projects focused on long-term SSA engagement strategy, progress monitoring and assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a responsive and flexible collaboration and support ecosystem that caters to stakeholders in the data for policy space at local, regional, and global levels • Efficient mobilisation of resources for sustainable capacity building, aimed at facilitating the participation of underrepresented regions and maximizing the impact of regional projects • Implementation of unique mission-driven leadership development models for policy-makers, addressing immediate skills shortage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bridging the gap between advanced computation and policy & practice • Facilitating efficient collaboration and knowledge sharing between disciplines & sectors, and at local, regional & global scales • Creating a more open, inclusive, and responsible research & innovation ecosystem • Enhancing public-private sector collaborations towards addressing grand challenges (climate change adaptation, gender equality etc.)

Proposed Regional Consortium Projects (Pilot)

Project 1: Navigating Complexity: Data, AI, and Advanced Computation in Decision-Making

Project 2: Fostering a Vibrant GovTech Industry across Africa

Project 3: Convergence of Technology and Grassroot Engagement

Thank you!

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